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Economy, Education and Society in 'New Normal' Phase

Emerging Issues, Challenges and Policies

**Mr. Rupai Hembram
Dr. Arabinda Roy
Mr. Mahabur Sarkar**
Editors

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Chapter 5

Global COVID-19 Pandemic has become a Challenge or Opening a Window of Opportunity? Scrutinizing from SDGs and Sustainability Perspectives

Arabinda Roy^{✉1} and Sanjeev Kumar²

Abstract The main intention of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is to transform our world with the enhancement of wealth and opportunity for a better tomorrow, which is considered as the “roadmap for humanity”. But the progress of human society is interrupted by the sudden outbreak of COVID-19 pandemic and as a result, the human-centric socioeconomic contexts have been experiencing enormous challenge and tremendous opportunities. The present chapter attempts to explore the impact and challenges of the COVID-19 pandemic on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in the “new *normal*” phase and to analyse the potential window of opportunities for sustainability transactions. Exploratory and qualitative research designs and descriptive analytical methods have been applied and for information, different authentic websites, different agencies, journals, and e-contents were searched. The study depicts that the COVID-19 pandemic not only poses a challenge for human society but also opens a potential window of opportunities for sustainability transactions, and finally some policy actions have been made for sustainability from socio-ecological perspectives.

Keywords Sustainability; SDGs; COVID-19 Epidemic; Challenges; Potential Window; *New Normal*

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5.1. Introduction

The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development is intended to eradicate poverty and guide the globe toward wealth and opportunity. In terms of the environment, economics, and global society, sustainable development goals address equality and responsibilities. The Sustainable Development Goals or Global Goals are a collection of 17 interlinked global goals designed to be a “shared blueprint for peace and prosperity for people and the planet, now and into the future”. The UN General Assembly established the SDGs in 2015, with the goal of achieving them by the year 2030. The SDGs are considered the “*roadmap for humanity*”. The Sustainable Development Goals are significantly hampered by discrimination in the distribution of resources all over the world. Worldwide, billions of people have expressed the desire for a brighter tomorrow. The leaders of the world selected 17 goals in 2015 to create a better future.

The sudden outbreak of COVID-19 epidemic is having a significant impact on the planet. It has caused disruptions in human activity and the basic requirements of the global population. Late in 2019, Wuhan, in the Hubei Province of Central China, saw the first sign of the pandemic, after which the entire world was under the virus' control. Around the world, the human-centric socioeconomic contexts have been experiencing an almost total standstill, creating a crisis in the human resource.

Reaching the 2030 Agenda and the Sustainable Development Goals will be extremely difficult, but there may also be a window of opportunity due to the epidemic (SDGs). There has been much debate regarding the potential long-term effects of the global COVID-19 epidemic on environmental sustainability. Almost all

facets of human and societal life have been disrupted since the COVID-19 pandemic's abrupt outbreak in late 2019 and the responses taken to combat it (hereinafter referred to as the COVID-19 crisis). These disruptions have frequently affected the environment as well as social natural systems.

In response to the COVID-19 pandemic, disease control strategies have been implemented that are both proactive and reactive, including lockdowns, physical segregation, and the usage of masks, and others initiative (**Andreucci and Marvuglia 2021; Andrijasevic et al. 2021; Aristovnik et al. 2020; Barberia et al. 2021; Leach et al. 2021; Lee and Woo 2020; Morea 2020; Rutjens et al. 2021; Zinn 2021a**). These policies have had an impact on almost every aspect of social life (**Oconnor et al. 2021; Ferreira and Serpa 2021**) which is serving as a “cultural break point” (**Lusardi and Tomelleri 2020**) both in the real world and online. According to **Echegaray (2021)** "These measures caused a “social recession” as they brought face-to-face interpersonal interaction to its minimum expression except among other household members, with social connections eventually migrating to the internet-mediated online sphere” (p. 568).

In a single word, the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic around the world not only affected the SDGs and their progress but also hampered the smooth functioning of human activities in all spheres of life and the progress of human society as a whole. The COVID-19 catastrophe may have opened a window of opportunity for societal change and environmental sustainability at the same time.

Under this background, the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and sustainability need

to be assessed. The present chapter will attempt to explore the concept of sustainability with respect to ecological, social, and economic perspectives and the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in the '*new normal*' phase. It also attempts to analyse whether the global COVID-19 pandemic is a challenge for sustainably developed society on the one hand and, on the other hand, whether it opens a window of opportunity?

The research design of the present chapter is exploratory and qualitative in design, and descriptive analytical methods have been applied. The information and data presented in the paper have been collected from different authentic websites of national and international agencies, journals, and e-contents. PubMed, Google Scholar and Research Gate platforms were searched for necessary actions.

This paper proceeds with the following sections: Section 5.2 discusses the concept of sustainable development, ideas of sustainability, its indicators, and typical approaches. Section 5.3 of the paper examines the progress of sustainable development Goals (SDGs) and consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic on the progress of human society as well as development with its different levels of variations. The fourth section (section 5.4) elaborates on the challenges of the post COVID-19 period to building a sustainably developed society, which is followed by section 5.5 analysing the potential window of opportunities for ecological, economic, and societal sustainability transitions. The last section of the paper is the concluding section, which elaborates on the policy options for the betterment of humans in the post COVID-19 periods.

5.2. The Sustainable Development and Sustainability: Key Concept and Misconceptions

The terms “sustainable development” and “sustainability” are frequently used interchangeably in modern discourse. However, sustainable development is not the same as sustainability. Sustainable development was first presented as an alternative to the growth ideology's development model in order to address growing concerns about growth limits and perceived injustices. Development that satisfies current demands without jeopardising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs is referred to as sustainable development. (**Emas 2015; Holden et al. 2014**).

This notion of sustainable development introduces two important ideas: the significance of the aspirations of the oppressed and the recognition of biophysical limitations. The first has been ignored by the majority, whilst the second is already relativized in the definition itself as a matter of technological advancement. (**Sneddon et al. 2006**). The 1987 Brundtland report on sustainable development is a seminal discussion on this concept (**Barkemeyer et al. 2014**).

The term “sustainability” has gained popularity in recent years, particularly in relation to environmental sustainability. Sustainability means a system may be maintained and renewed within a typical balance of lifecycles without being depleted or extinct. Defining sustainability as merely about the natural environment is incomplete as it ignores the social systems that intertwine with the environment. The sustainability of the wider ecological system is determined by the elements of various social systems. Social systems include, but are not limited to, worldviews,

culture, the economy, politics, families, and community subsystems, all of which contribute to overall sustainability. The development of sound and equitable political, economic, family and community institutions that also support the environment must be considered in efforts to attain sustainability.

To understand the concept of sustainability, it is necessary to clarify two basic ideas. The first is sustainability indicators, and the second is typical approaches to sustainability indicators (**Innes and Booher 2000**). Sustainability indicators can be classified as individual indicators, thematic indicators, and composite indicators, and there are four typical approaches to sustainability. However, the details of the idea of sustainability, its indicators, and typical approaches are presented in **Fig. 5.1**.

5.3. Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), its Progress and Hard-hit by the COVID-19 Pandemic

Prior to the pandemic, there had been uneven progress toward achieving all 17 SDGs (**Barbier and Burgess 2020; United Nations 2020; Moyer and Hedden 2020**). Since 2000, there has been an extreme level of decline in poverty and infant and maternal mortality all over the world, and it is well established that low-income countries have achieved less poverty reduction (**Barbier and Burgess 2020**).

The sudden outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic all over the world has devastating consequences for the progress of human society as well as development, although there are regional and national level variations. The developing nations have been particularly hard-hit

by COVID-19. The pandemic is expected to have a negative effect on 12 of the 17 SDGs targets (Ahmed et al. 2020; Sumner et al. 2020). Fig 5.2 indicates the impact of COVID-19 pandemic on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Fig. 5.1: Conceptualizing sustainability, its indicators and typical approaches
Source: The authors.

Fig.5.2: The impact of COVID-19 on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Source: Adapted from UN (2020) Figure 5 and modified by the authors.

In a report on 'Global Solidarity: Responding to the socioeconomic impacts of COVID-19 by the United Nations in the year 2020 (United Nations 2020), it is highlighted that there are still 673 million people who use open defecation, 736 million people who live in extreme poverty line, 785 million people who lack even basic access to clean drinking water, and 821 million people who are undernourished. It is also evident from the above mentioned

report that still 87% of the population lives in rural areas, 840 million people are without electricity, and 3 billion people face a lack of clean cooking fuels and technology.

Perhaps never has the COVID-19 pandemic brought the importance of development-which offers not only equitable economic growth but also sustainable use of the planet's natural resources-more into sharp relief. The Decade for Action to realise the 17 SDGs established by the UN Agenda 2030 begins in the year 2020.

The 17 goals serve as the global road map for eradicating poverty, preserving the environment, and ensuring prosperity. The Global Commission on the Economy and Climate (GCEC) had reached the following conclusion prior to COVID-19:

“Strong climate action has the potential to generate over 65 million new low-carbon jobs by 2030, deliver at least \$26 trillion in net global economic benefits, and avoid 700,000 premature deaths from air pollution” (GCEC 2018).

Since the adaptation of SDGs in 2015, it is concludes that East, South, and Southeast Asia are the regions that have progressed most on the SDG Index, which is presented in **Fig. 5.3**.

5.4. Sustainably Developed Society: The Challenges of Post-COVID-19 Period

The matter of sustainability, specifically the development of a sustainable society, is a challenging task in the post COVID-19 period, mainly due to the interdisciplinary nature of sustainability. The development and enhancement of a sustainable society depends on multiple and interdependent factors, such as health,

social, economic, ecological, political, educational, and moral areas (Serpa and Ferreira 2020). Undoubtedly, the success and fulfilment of the 2030 UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is a complex process, and human beings with their proper utilisation are the leading agents for the changes in socio-cultural pattern of future sustainable society.

Fig. 5.3: Levels and trends of SDGs for East, South, and Southeast Asia, 2020

Source: Prepared by the authors based on Sustainable Development Report 2020.

However, the unexpected and unplanned outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic was a generator of high uncertainty about the present but also about the future (Ferreira et al. 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic changes the social chain, the social process, as well as

the whole social system with its unpredictable directions. Moreover, it can be considered that the pandemic opens a potential window for future sustainable development opportunities to (re)discover the new world and fulfilment of SDGs. In the words one of the famous sociologists of Melbourn University (**Zinn 2021b**), the potential opportunities can be expressed as “To what extent the opportunity for global learning is taken up remains to be seen. There is little doubt, however, that pandemics will contribute to long-term changes in human attitudes and behaviour towards the environment and the technologically shaped lifeworld” (p. 603).

5.5. The Global COVID-19 Pandemic as a Window of Opportunity for Sustainability

The COVID-19 crisis has likely created a potential window of opportunity for societal change and environmental sustainability (**Lehmann et al. 2021**). Environmental sustainability is the nexus between the COVID-19 pandemic and the societal transitions towards sustainability. The COVID-19 situation might offer a window of opportunity for speeding up sustainability transitions on a global scale, but this goal can only be reached with deliberate planning and well-crafted strategic communication in the public sphere. No doubt, it is true that the COVID-19 pandemic can provide a window of opportunity for promoting sustainability transitions in consumption and production. According to **Cohen (2020)** “The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic is simultaneously a public health emergency and a real-time experiment in downsizing the consumer economy” (p.1). The current COVID-19 pandemic and its potential to pave the way for sustainability transitions are discursively linked in this policy brief in a way that is beneficial, quick, and mindful of the difficult social

and psychological conditions in which societies around the world currently find themselves.

5.5.1. Opportunities for Ecological, Economic and Societal Sustainability Transitions

We believe the notion of “opportunity” needs to be used very carefully. How vulnerable people and societies are will play a significant role in whether or not the COVID-19 crisis offers an opportunity for personal and political reform. When shaping public debate in the upcoming months, the word “opportunity” should be used with caution. It could be better to promote the idea that future transitions toward sustainability offer a chance to make something good from a very challenging circumstance. Nevertheless, the expression is used in this context because it is the accepted academic term for transitions studies.

It is important to recognise the psychological and psychosocial toll that the current state has on people, families, and entire civilizations. There is a close connection between the COVID-19 pandemic and unsustainable behaviours. There are numerous connections between the onset and seriousness of the COVID-19 pandemic and actions that are not socially, economically, or ecologically sustainable. Regarding environmental concerns, studies have highlighted the importance of large-scale land use changes, such as agricultural intensification, mining, road building, and deforestation, and the accompanying loss of habitats and biodiversity in raising the risk that infections will move from wildlife to humans as zoonotic diseases (**IPBES 2019; Scott 2020; Daszak 2020**).

However, making imprudent economic decisions has a negative impact on the environment as well as contributes to pandemics. Instead, while fiscally irresponsible actions did not result in the coronavirus pandemic, they undoubtedly aided in making the current crisis so severe and all-encompassing. The world's economy is particularly susceptible to disruption because of the high level of globalisation, just-in-time manufacturing, and dense concentration of production facilities in just a few low-wage nations, particularly China (**Parsons 2020**).

Last but not least, the lack of importance placed on social dimensions of sustainability, such as the low pay and low prestige accorded to workers in the care economy, as well as the strict imposition of a for-(maximum)-profit orientation onto the healthcare industry, make this situation tougher to resolve. Even in the most developed nations in the world, there are not enough beds, respirators, or staff working in intensive care units to handle a pandemic-level influx of patients (**Mihm 2020**).

In short, the devastation of coronavirus outbreak was caused by three factors: a lack of ecological sustainability, a lack of economic sustainability, and a lack of social sustainability.

5.5.2. Opportunities Offer for Sustainability Transitions Research on Electricity

The COVID-19 pandemic has a significant impact on many socio-technical systems and offers a rare chance to examine in real time the consequences of a prolonged disruption at the landscape scale on the trajectories of sustainable transitions. The COVID-19 pandemic's long-term effects are likely to bring about further long-lasting changes related to the digitization of work and other daily

activities, which will lessen the demand for travel and overall fossil-energy use. The COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant influence on some countries' energy sectors, causing a decline in demand and lower prices for oil, gas, and power (**Mylenka and Novyj 2020**). Due to the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic, electricity demand in countries, such as the UK, has declined over the last months as a result of factories and other businesses halting their operations (**Thomas 2020**), and patterns of demand and supply changing as domestic demand increases and commercial and industrial demand drops (**Lempriere 2020**).

Due to the adoption of digital technologies for remote labour, information exchange, and communication, as well as the closure of some sectors, the pandemic has highlighted the value of energy in society. Because there may be less need to employ non-renewable energy sources to meet power demand if total electricity consumption declines, the share of generation from renewable sources can be greatly raised and maintained (**Biol 2020**).

5.6. Conclusions

In this article, the authors explored the nexus between sustainable development goals along with sustainability transactions and the challenges and or opportunities of the COVID-19 crisis towards socio economic as well as environmental sustainability. Present analysis builds on an exploratory and qualitative research design method which helps to understand the structure regarding this nexus and to investigate them in terms of their presumptions, content and reliability.

The authors of the present chapter first examined the concept of sustainable development and SDGs along with the key concept and approach of sustainability and, thereafter, highlighted the devastating consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic on Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The crisis of the pandemic not only hampers the progress of development and well-being of society but also affects the progress of transitions towards environmental sustainability. Simultaneously, it can be confirmed that this pandemic likely creates a potential window of opportunity for socio-ecological change.

The extraordinary scenario brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic has serious implications for society, and how these implications are managed and how policies are implemented will have an impact on future developments. The pandemic has acted as a catalyst for changes in key industries and has brought attention to how interconnected the sustainability concerns addressed by the SDGs are. The effects of the lockdown, including forced home offices, forced online learning, less mobility, shorter hours of work, etc., have increased social structural injustice and inequality (SDG5) (SDG10). Additionally, observations and analysis point to stronger linkages between SDG4, SDG8, SDG3, and SDG13.

However, the pandemic has created a rare chance for change as more people are becoming aware of the urgency with which sustainability challenges must be resolved and the significance that balanced ecosystems have for health and wellness. Additionally, the need for innovation (SDG9) and cooperation are expanding (SDG17). Consequently, it's critical to take advantage of the chance to rebuild and recover from the pandemic in a way that addresses sustainable development and strengthens community resilience.

The pandemic has given people a chance to pause, reflect, and possibly adjust their current behaviours. Utilizing this window of opportunity to “build back better” is possible (OECD 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic has become the challenge of the post-COVID-19 era for building up a sustainably developed society. Scientists, policy makers, and social workers always try to maintain the sustainability of the new world. However, the crisis created by the COVID-19 pandemic around the world implores us not only to attend to and think about ecological justice, ecosocial worldview, but also re-examine our worldviews that landed us in these predicaments.

In conclusion, the COVID-19 crisis's disruptive shocks, the substantial public recovery funds supplied, and more generally, the widespread popular support for political action to ameliorate the crisis have undoubtedly created a window of opportunity for social reform. The size of this window, however, is dependent on the particular regional setting in which society and individual decisions are made. Additionally, only when individual adjustments are coupled with political changes built on clever and focused recovery programmes does this present a genuine potential for reducing unfavourable environmental change. In order to achieve a recovery that takes into account issues related to the environment, the economy, and society, these policies must be included in a truly sustainable narrative. More particular, recovery initiatives should be planned to coincide with the necessary long-term sustainability shifts. In other words, policymakers, businesses, scientists, and civil society must actively turn COVID-19 into a chance for sustainability.

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